

Signs of the Sojourner

Developed by: Echodog Games

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Keywords

Abuse, Communication Dynamics, Communication Studies, Empathy, Ethical Decision-making, Relationships, Self-reflection

Introduction

Signs of the Sojourner is a narrative-driven card game developed by Echodog Games and released in 2020. The game revolves around the themes of communication and relationships. The player assumes the role of a character who takes over their mother's shop after her death and embarks on journeys to collect new goods. Along the way, the player encounters various characters with whom they interact through card play. The deck of cards represents the character's experiences and relationships and evolves throughout the game.

The story of *Signs of the Sojourner* is very relatable through the protagonist's relationship with their mother and a close friend. These emotional connections add a vivid, profound layer to the narrative, motivating the player to collect goods from the game world for the shop. This personal journey and its associated challenges make the story not only captivating but also meaningful.

Additionally, the game offers multiple endings depending on the player's decisions, which adds to its replayability and depth. Each choice influences the direction of the story and the relationships, leading to a variety of possible conclusions.

A particularly emotional moment in the game is when the initial attempts to gather enough goods to keep the shop running fail. These moments of disappointment and frustration, when the protagonist is forced to give up, deepen the emotional aspect of the story. They illustrate the real-life challenges one can face, making the successes in the game all the more meaningful.

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	Echodog Games
Game type:	Digital Card Game
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	Approximately 30 minutes to several hours, depending on game pace

Languages:	Available in multiple languages, including English and German
Environment:	PC or Mac with internet connection
Material:	All necessary materials are available online
Price:	One-time purchase, no subscription required

Resonance & Criticism

Signs of the Sojourner has been praised for its innovative game mechanics and deep narrative. It stands out from other games for its unique portrayal of communication and relationships. Critics have highlighted that the game offers an empathetic and thoughtful gaming experience. The game has established itself as a valuable tool for understanding communication dynamics.

It received a significant recognition at DreamHack Anaheim 2020, where it won the Best RPG Award in the Indie Playground. This award underscores the game's creative excellence and innovative approach to depicting interpersonal interactions.

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. In-game screenshot showing the card-based communication system in *Signs of the Sojourner* (Echodog Games). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

In *Signs of the Sojourner*, everything revolves around interacting with various characters through card play. Each card represents a communication pattern, and the player must connect these patterns to have successful conversations (see Figure 1). The player's deck evolves over the course of the game based on their experiences and decisions.

Simple communication concepts are introduced at the beginning, while the tasks become increasingly complex as the game progresses. Players must learn to strategically use their cards to achieve successful interactions, with each decision having consequences for relationships and the progression of the story.

Throughout the game, special events, such as an earthquake, affect the dynamics of communication. In this situation, an additional communication style, referred to as "Grief," is introduced. This extension adds additional emotional depth to interactions and highlights the impact of external events on communication.

Initially, the player possesses only cards from the starting area, featuring circles and triangles. Depending on where the player travels, they can randomly acquire new cards on the way or during conversations. However, they must always give up one card, so the number of cards in the deck remains the same. The game is turn-based and consists of 5 rounds during which the player can explore the world of Signs of the Sojourner. The player has 50 days to complete tasks and explore locations. During this time, the player accumulates fatigue cards that cannot be used in conversations but still take up space in the deck. As the game progresses, it becomes more difficult to have successful conversations.

There is a caravan that the player can accompany through the world. However, not all locations are unlocked at the beginning. The player must find out through successful conversations how to reach new locations. Characters provide information about available routes, allowing each round to be individually designed. Each game can thus be individually designed through this mechanic. However, there are advantages to staying with the caravan, such as more tasks and more goods received.

Each area has two preferred communication styles. Since players receive cards corresponding to the area after a conversation, the first conversations in new regions are often complex. The longer the game goes on, the more complicated the card mechanics become. For example, special effects can be included randomly, increasing complexity and motivating players to use different tactics.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Signs of the Sojourner aims to provide players with a deeper understanding of communication dynamics and interpersonal relationships. The game promotes empathy and self-reflection by immersing players in various social interactions and encouraging them to reflect on the impact of their choices.

The game is particularly useful in educational settings to teach topics such as communication, decision-making, and empathy. It can be used in courses that focus on psychology, sociology, and interpersonal communication.

Effectiveness

Although there are no specific studies on the effectiveness of Signs of the Sojourner as a learning material, playful experiences suggest that the game can improve players' ability to recognize and manage complex communication situations. Immediate feedback and the opportunity to learn from mistakes promote problem-solving and self-reflection.

The study by Barr (2018) shows that commercial video games can contribute to the development of skills such as communication, adaptability, and resource management. These findings support the assumption that Signs of the Sojourner can also help to promote communication skills through its playful elements.

Overall, Signs of the Sojourner cleverly combines the elements of an adventure game with the teaching of communication skills. The direct link between the cards played and the game's visible actions makes the abstract topic of communication more lively and motivating.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

While Signs of the Sojourner aims to represent communication patterns through card game mechanics, it eventually became clear that the cards functioned more as elements of color compatibility rather than actual communication tools. Since it was previously known which two communication styles a character had, it was less about communicative difficulties and more about the compatibility of the cards. This could lead players to focus more on the strategic selection of cards rather than engaging with the deeper aspects of communication.

For my taste, it would have been more interesting if the game had offered the possibility of responding to assertive characters with empathy and soothing them over the course of communication. This would have added more depth to the card mechanics and focused more on actual communication rather than just choosing the right color. Thus, the cards often remain tools that need to fit, without representing the diversity of real communicative challenges.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Barr, M. (2018). Student attitudes to games-based skills development: Learning from video games in higher education. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 80, 283–294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2017.11.030>

Echodog Games. (2020). *Signs of the Sojourner* [Video game]. PC.

